

Principles and models of physical education.

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Annatatsiya: Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va amaliyoti umumiy printsiplari va jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi usuliyatining printsiplari deb ataladigan printsiplarga tayanadi: Bo'lardan tashqari, jismoniy tarbiyaning ayrim ko'rinishlari va xususiyatlarini ifodalovchi (masalan, sport, trenirovkasi, kosmonavtlar, o't o'chiruvchilar trenirovkasi va hokazo) printsiplari ham mavjud.

Annotation: The general principles of the theory and practice of physical education and the principles of the methodology of the theory of physical education are based on the principles of: etc.) principles are also available.

Аннотация: Общие принципы теории и практики физического воспитания и принципы методологии теории физического воспитания основаны на принципах: и т. д.) принципы также имеются.

Kalit so'z: sport, trenirovkasi, kosmonavtlar, o't o'chiruvchilar trenirovkasi, printsiplari, sog'lomlashtirish

Key word: sport, training, training of astronauts, firefighters, principles, health

Ключевые слова: спорт, подготовка, подготовка космонавтов, пожарных, принципы, здоровье.

The theory and practice of physical education are inextricably linked and form a single system of principles. First of all, let's get acquainted with the general principles of the theory of physical education.

- They are: a) connection of physical training with work and military practice;
b) comprehensive development of a person;
c) is grouped as the principle of orientation of physical education to health.

Theoretical principles in the process of physical education, on the one hand, serve as regulations, and on the other hand, in the process of physical education, they put the teacher in a theoretically and methodologically certain framework (mould), direction. In the pedagogical process and practical activity, the principle can become important in the form of obligation and law.

In some cases: we consider the principle as a part of certain knowledge in physical education, or as a guide (instructor) for activity, or as a general basis for performing various specific tasks.

General principles of the theory of physical education

The theory and practice of physical education is based on the so-called principles of the theory and method of physical education:) principles are also available. They are inextricably linked and form a single system of principles. First of all, let's get acquainted with the general principles of the theory of physical education. They are: a) connection of physical training with labor and military practice; b) comprehensive development of a person; c) is grouped as the principle of orientation of physical education to health.

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The principle of directing physical education to health

The principle that physical education is aimed at improving health implies the responsibility of the participants to respond to their health when they are engaged in physical exercises. Organizers of physical culture, trainers are not only responsible for the health of the participants before the state and the people, but also for its strengthening and improvement.

It gives a positive effect only if physical exercises are done under the supervision of a doctor and a teacher. Improper use can have a negative effect on the health of the practitioner. Therefore, taking into account biological characteristics - age, sex, health, systematic supervision by a doctor and a teacher is a leading factor in the educational process.

In practice, working without a plan has very negative consequences. A minor mistake of the pedagogue in choosing the chosen methods, the standard of exercises, the intensity of execution, the total amount of training can be very expensive for the student.

It is possible to encounter such situations that a temporary increase in sports results, an increase in physical fitness indicators, can lead to temporary pathological changes in the body that are not noticeable to the athlete. The bad consequences that arise have a negative impact on the reputation of physical culture and sports.

For this reason, the main attention should be focused on their analysis, not limited to the recognition of evidence of medical supervision.

Unsystematic control inevitably leads to negative consequences.

The principle of connecting physical education with health requires daily regular communication between the doctor, pedagogue and practitioner.

The principles of physical education are interconnected. Only then will they remain relevant.

The connection of physical education with work and military practice is its leading principle. This principle represents the main law of physical education in our country, its importance for the creative work of members of our society

Methods of organizing students' activities in the physical education class

By management of students' activities, we understand the methodology of organizing physical exercises according to the teacher's plan during training.

In the process of education, physical education teachers organize the activities of students in physical education lessons individually (frontally), continuously, by dividing them into groups, individually and by walking around.

1. The frontal method of organizing the student's activities is to separate all the students in the group

it is understood that he completes the exercise together with the teacher to solve the same task. The advantage of this methodology is that all students are equally involved in performing the exercise and they are occupied individually, high density is achieved in the lesson (session), and the speed, intensity and norm of loading are the same for everyone.

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This methodology is mainly used in the preparatory and final parts of the lesson, in mastering and improving new material, and in training with younger students. 2. The method of continuous organization of the student's activity. It manifests itself in the way of full performance of movement activity without explaining the order of performing the exercise, adapting the methodical instructions to the rhythm of the movement, without stopping the group to correct mistakes, in order to achieve high intensity. The advantage of this methodology is to achieve the same loading norm, volume, and intensity for all students in the group (regardless of their physical fitness). This creates an opportunity to assess the general physical fitness of the students of the class and group, especially to compare and compare the level of exercise opportunities of the students themselves compared to their peers. It is mainly used in the preparatory and final parts of the lesson, and in the main part of the lesson, where the mastering of new material begins.

3. The content of the method of dividing the study group (class) into groups, taking into account the physical development, physical fitness, the variety of tasks set in the lesson, and the necessary equipment for solving them, divides a large group of students into small, is to divide into small groups. This methodology is mainly used in the main part of the lesson.

The method of organizing the student's activities and dividing them into groups creates an opportunity to take into account their physical development and physical fitness during the educational process. This, in turn, makes the teaching process more effective, takes physical capabilities into account, and saves time spent on the educational process. This methodology places the responsibility of the teacher on the preparation of a group activist who is prepared in advance, knows the techniques of the subject, and is able to perform the task of leading a group. 4. The method of individual organization of student activity is mainly used in the repetition lessons of the subjects of the academic year, academic term, sections of the State Standard program. Individual organization of students' activities requires students to acquire theoretical and practical knowledge in a technical manner, to ensure the safety of themselves and their teammates, to be able to show the exercise and, most importantly, to be mastered, introduced, strengthened and the training material being improved must be a familiar material for the students with pre-taught exercise techniques. In addition, in some classes, students are assigned tasks from topics or exercises that they have not mastered during the academic year. It is recommended to use this method mainly in classes conducted with students of secondary and senior school age. 5. Organization of the student's activity through the method of performing exercises in a circle, mainly with students of upper classes, after learning the planned educational material, moving from one exercise to another, the teacher's command (signal) , after performing the exercise without a signal, it is organized in the way of switching to another device in order to change places. The effectiveness of this method is that it saves time, all students are busy, they develop the need for independent work and instructor skills. There are four variations of this technique called "Krestring".

Independent work of students can be seen as a separate form of organizing classes, and as a method of organizing student activities to solve set tasks. The main and specific goal of teaching independent work is to train students to be independent in training.

The first signs of the student's ability to work independently in his work are manifested by working without outside help or with an insignificant level of help.

The level of the student's independence depends on his age-specific understanding and the content of the educational material.

Physical technical and tactical training of the athlete

Sports training has two directions; including general and special physical training (MJT) process unites In the process of general physical training (UJT), on the basis of the general development of organs, systems and functions, it creates and expands the existing conditions for sports specialization, as well as enriches the relationships of its various movements, skills and abilities. Special training ensures the development of qualities and abilities specific to a specific sport, as well as equips it with technical and tactical knowledge and skills.

Neither general training nor special training can be removed from the training process or replaced by one. Because there is an interdependence between general and special preparation. It is impossible to draw a border between them. Based on this, some experts suggest not to separate these aspects of sports training. In our opinion, general and special training differ somewhat with their specific functions, tools, methods, and training processes. Specific physical training is an important factor in sports specialization, and general physical training It is a factor that indirectly affects the process of specialization through various connections between one or another aspect of the athlete's development.

The general training of the athlete should also reflect the characteristics of his specialty. Because positive and negative effects occur during individual physical exercises, limiting the general preparation to be the same in different sports.

As we have seen, general training is different in different sports, but it cannot be confused with special training.

General and special training is a continuous process that is always carried out for many years in sports training: a number of authors try to convince that as the athlete's skill increases, the number of general physical training sessions and the time allocated to them should be reduced.

The size of the UJT should be reduced not at the expense of reducing the time allocated to it, but at the expense of more work on special physical training. As for the interaction of UJT and MJT in the training series, it is expressed as follows: in the I stage of the training period, especially in the foundation mesocycle, UJT dominates, then it gradually decreases, in the II stage of preparation and during the competition, MJT increases, during this period, UJT is active takes a central place in the form of recreation.

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